

NAVIGATING HUMAN-WILDLIFE CONFLICT: LEGAL FRAMEWORKS FOR HUMAN-WILDLIFE HARMONY IN KERALA AND KARNATAKA STATES

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ABSTRACT

As human populations grow, we encounter wild animals more often as we move into their space. Sometimes these interactions are negative this is called human-wildlife conflict. However, through the work that we do across the world, we are beginning to see that humans can live alongside wildlife in a way that is helpful to both of us. Human-wildlife conflicts in India, particularly in the biodiversity-rich states of Kerala and Karnataka, have intensified in recent years. This paper critically examines the legal and policy frameworks required to address the growing cross-jurisdictional challenges posed by human-wildlife conflicts. By exploring recent interstate agreements, reviewing state-specific wildlife protection laws, and comparing international best practices, the paper aims to propose a set of comprehensive legal and policy solutions.

Keywords: Wild life, Bio-Diversit, Wildlife habitats & Legislative Reform

INTRODUCTION

The human wildlife conflicts occur when human activities overlap with wildlife habitats, often resulting in the destruction of crops, property, and, in extreme cases, human lives. Both states have been grappling with increasing interactions between humans and wildlife, especially in forested and rural areas adjacent to protected reserves.¹ Wildlife does not recognize the human-imposed boundaries that divide landscapes into states, cities, and agricultural lands. For animals, forests, rivers, and grasslands form a continuous ecosystem, essential for their survival. However, as wildlife moves across state borders in search of food, mates, or habitat, they often enter human settlements and face the complexities of man-made jurisdictions. These natural migrations frequently result in human-wildlife conflicts.

Management of Human wildlife conflict in India is an urgent and important issue. It is necessary to address the issue in a holistic manner, and co-create the mitigation solutions, with full engagement of all the relevant stakeholders. The project “Human-Wildlife Conflict Mitigation in India” (HWC) takes the approach of harmonious coexistence, by ensuring that both human and wildlife are protected from conflicts. This approach follows the modern wildlife conservation principles to balance the needs of people with the conservation of nature.² It also highlights the importance of collaboration between states and local communities, the role of technology in conflict mitigation, and the potential of Indian knowledge system and legislative reforms such as the Wildlife Protection (Amendment) Bill, 2023, to address these complex issues.

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¹ K. Singh, "The Rise of Human-Wildlife Conflicts in India," *Journal of Environmental Law* (2020) 45, 310

² Human-Wildlife Conflict Mitigation in India (HWC) Project description Title: Human-Wildlife Conflict Mitigation in India Commissioned by: Federal Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ) Country: India Lead executing agency: Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change Overall term: 2017 to 2023

THE ESCALATING HUMAN-WILDLIFE CONFLICTS IN KERALA AND KARNATAKA: A GROWING CHALLENGE

Deforestation and Habitat Fragmentation

The primary drivers of human-wildlife conflicts are deforestation, encroachment, and infrastructure development in forest areas. Both Kerala and Karnataka have experienced significant loss of forest cover due to agricultural expansion, illegal logging, and urbanization.³ This has fragmented wildlife habitats and pushed animals into human settlements, leading to conflicts.

Climate Change and Resource Scarcity

Climate change has exacerbated these conflicts, with irregular rainfall and changes in vegetation patterns forcing wildlife to migrate in search of food and water.⁴ In regions like Wayanad⁵ in Kerala and Bandipur⁶ in Karnataka, elephants and leopards are known to frequently raid crops and livestock, causing significant economic losses for farmers.⁷

Human Population Growth: The expanding human population encroaches upon natural habitats, bringing humans and wildlife into closer proximity and increasing the likelihood of conflicts.

Agricultural Expansion: As agricultural activities expand into wildlife habitats, conflicts arise over competition for resources such as land, water, and food. Crop raiding by wildlife can result in significant economic losses for farmers.

Infrastructure Development: The construction of roads, highways, dams, and other infrastructure projects can fragment and degrade wildlife habitats, disrupting migration routes and dispersal patterns, and leading to increased human-wildlife encounters.

Illegal Wildlife Trade: Poaching and illegal wildlife trade contribute to the decline of many species, leading to conflicts as dwindling populations of certain species come into closer contact with humans.

Urbanization: Urban expansion results in the conversion of natural habitats into built-up areas, forcing wildlife to adapt to new environments or migrate to urban fringes, where conflicts with humans are more likely to occur.

³ Wildlife Protection (Amendment) Bill 2023 (India).

⁴ S. Sharma, "Deforestation and Wildlife Habitat Loss in the Western Ghats," *Environmental Conservation* (2019) 54, 120.

⁵ https://forest.kerala.gov.in/images/ForestStatistics/FINAL_2020_FS_PRINT_WEB.pdf Northern circle Division total page 3

⁶ [https://aranya.gov.in/aranyacms/\(S\(wtbnngjydxskktgro1ycxhl3c\)\)/English/AnnualReports.aspx](https://aranya.gov.in/aranyacms/(S(wtbnngjydxskktgro1ycxhl3c))/English/AnnualReports.aspx)

⁷ M. Das, "Impact of Climate Change on Wildlife Movements in India," *Indian Journal of Environmental Studies* (2021) 32, 8

Land Use Changes: Deforestation, conversion of natural habitats for agriculture or urban development, and habitat degradation due to unsustainable land use practices all contribute to habitat loss and fragmentation, increasing the likelihood of conflicts between humans and wildlife. Addressing human-wildlife conflicts requires a multi-faceted approach that involves habitat conservation, land use planning, sustainable development practices, community engagement, and conflict resolution strategies. By addressing the underlying drivers of conflicts and promoting coexistence between humans and wildlife, it is possible to mitigate the negative impacts on both people and wildlife.

LEGAL FRAMEWORK GOVERNING HUMAN-WILDLIFE CONFLICT

Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972

The Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972, is the cornerstone of wildlife conservation law in India.⁸ The Act provides for the protection of species and their habitats by creating national parks, wildlife sanctuaries, and protected areas. It also contains provisions for penalizing poaching and illegal wildlife trade.⁹ However, the Act does not directly address the mitigation of human-wildlife conflict, leaving gaps in the legal framework.¹⁰

The Scheduled Tribes and Other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act, 2006

The Scheduled Tribes and Other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act, 2006, is a key piece of forest legislation passed in India on 18 December 2006.¹¹ It has also been called the Forest Rights Act, the Tribal Rights Act, the Tribal Bill, and the Tribal Land Act. The Forest Rights Act (FRA), 2006, recognizes the rights of forest-dwelling communities, allowing them to live in and use forest resources for livelihood purposes.¹² While the Act aims to balance the rights of indigenous people with conservation objectives, it has sometimes led to tensions between forest communities and wildlife conservation efforts.¹³ In areas of Kerala and Karnataka, this has created challenges for managing conflicts between forest dwellers and wildlife.¹⁴

Wildlife Protection (Amendment) Bill, 2023

The Wildlife Protection (Amendment) Bill, 2023, introduced in Parliament, aims to address some of the shortcomings in the Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972.¹⁵ The Bill seeks to strengthen wildlife conservation efforts by enhancing penalties for wildlife crimes, expanding the scope

⁸ Forest Department of Karnataka, "Human-Wildlife Conflict Data," (2022) 7.

⁷ Wildlife (Protection) Act 1972 (India).

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ The Scheduled Tribes and Other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition Of Forest Rights) Act, 2006 <https://www.indiacode.nic.in/bitstream/123456789/8311/1/a2007-02.pdf>

¹² S. Kulkarni, "Legal Gaps in Wildlife Conflict Management in India," *Law, Environment, and Development Journal* (2022) 28, 340.

¹³ Forest Rights Act 2006 (India).

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ M. Nair, "Community Rights vs Conservation Efforts: A Study of Kerala and Karnataka," *South Asia Conservation Studies* (2020) 13, 45.

of protected species, and creating a more robust framework for the management of protected areas.¹⁶Crucially, the Bill introduces provisions to address human-wildlife conflict mitigation, which include,Increased financial support for communities affected by human-wildlife conflict.A greater role for local governments in managing and preventing conflicts.¹⁷The Bill is expected to fill the existing legal gaps and offer more effective tools for states like Kerala and Karnataka in handling human-wildlife conflicts.¹⁸

The Forest (Conservation) Amendment Bill, 2023

The Indian Forest Act, 1927 was framed with the objective of managing timber and other forest resources.¹⁹It provides for state governments to notify any forest land they own as reserved or protected forests. All land rights in such land are subject to the provisions of the Act. The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980, was enacted to prevent large-scale deforestation.²⁰It requires the central government's approval for any diversion of forest land for non-forest purposes.²¹The Bill amends the Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980 to make it applicable to certain types of land. These include land notified as a forest under the Indian Forest Act, 1927 or in government records after the 1980 Act came into effect. The Act will not be applicable for land converted to non-forest use before December 12, 1996.It also exempts certain types of land from the purview of the Act. These include land within 100 km of India's border needed for national security projects, small roadside amenities, and public roads leading to a habitation.

The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023

Though the BNS focuses primarily on crimes like terrorism, corruption, and organized crime, it may influence human-wildlife conflict cases by setting precedents for public nuisance, negligence, and property damage. Sections that deal with causing harm to public safety or the environment may be applicable to human-wildlife conflict scenarios, particularly when negligence or intentional harm to wildlife leads to endangerment of human lives or vice versa. The BNS.²² focuses on modernizing penal provisions around negligence, which could extend to the actions of individuals or corporations responsible for habitat destruction, leading to wildlife intrusion into human areas. Under the BNS, if such negligence results in injury or death (to either humans or wildlife), stricter penalties might be enforced.

POLICY INTERVENTIONS IN TACKLING HUMAN-WILDLIFE CONFLICTS IN KERALA AND KARNATAKA

¹⁶ Wildlife Protection (Amendment) Bill 2023 (India).

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ Ibid.

¹⁹ https://www.naredco.in/notification/pdfs/Final_Report_of_HLC.pdf

²⁰ The Forest (Conservation) Bill, 1980, as introduced in Lok Sabha.

²¹ <https://www.indiacode.nic.in/bitstream/123456789/1760/1/forestAA1980.pdf>

²² https://www.mha.gov.in/sites/default/files/250883_english_01042024.pdf Ministry Of Law And Justice (Legislative Department) New Delhi, the 25th December, 2023/Pausha 4, 1945 (Saka)The following Act of Parliament received the assent of the President on the25th December, 2023 and is hereby published for general information: THE BHARATIYA NYAYA SANHITA, 2023 NO. 45 OF 2023[25th December, 2023.]

Compensation Schemes for Farmers

The measures taken by the governments of Kerala and Karnataka to address human-wildlife conflicts. Both Kerala and Karnataka have introduced compensation schemes to mitigate the economic impact of human-wildlife conflict. These schemes provide financial relief to farmers who suffer crop or livestock loss due to wildlife raids.²³ However, the process for obtaining compensation has been criticized for being slow and bureaucratic. In recent years, efforts have been made to streamline the process, and the use of technology, such as mobile apps, has improved the reporting and verification of damage.

Community-Based Conservation

Involving local communities in conservation efforts has been a key strategy for mitigating human-wildlife conflict. In Kerala, initiatives such as the "Vayalvaram" project²⁴ focus on restoring wetlands and creating buffer zones to prevent wildlife from entering human settlements. Similarly, in Karnataka, the Forest Department has worked with tribal communities to monitor and manage wildlife movements.

Technology for Conflict Mitigation

The use of technology has played a crucial role in reducing human-wildlife conflict in both states. The Forest Departments of Kerala and Karnataka have employed GPS tracking systems to monitor the movement of elephants and other animals. Drones are also used to detect wildlife presence near human settlements, allowing authorities to intervene before conflicts escalate. Human-wildlife conflict is a growing issue in states with rich biodiversity like Kerala and Karnataka. This conflict escalates when human activities encroach on wildlife habitats, leading to property damage or loss of life. One such conflict zone is the Chaka Koban region, located along the Kerala-Karnataka border.²⁵ The region is a hotspot for wildlife activity, and both states have faced significant challenges managing human-animal interactions. The dispute over the area and its management of wildlife interactions has sparked tension between both states.²⁶

Cross-State Collaboration and Coordination

The shared forest areas between Kerala and Karnataka, particularly in regions like the Western Ghats, necessitate coordination between the two states. However, cross-border

²³ P. Rao "Legal Reforms for Wildlife Conservation in India," *Journal of Indian Environmental Law* (2023) 38, 22.

²⁴ <https://spb.kerala.gov.in/en/major-Initiatives-decentralised>

²⁵ Chaka Koban is a dense forest area that is home to a variety of species, including elephants, leopards, and tigers. The region has become notorious for frequent human-wildlife encounters, largely due to deforestation, encroachment, and expanding agricultural activities. The geographical overlap between Kerala and Karnataka adds another layer of complexity to the dispute, as both states claim jurisdiction over certain areas of the forest, complicating conservation and conflict mitigation efforts.

²⁶ For instance, in 2021, the Kerala Forest Department recorded a sharp rise in human-elephant conflicts, with over 200 cases of crop damage in Chaka Koban. [Kerala Forest Department, Annual Report 2021, p. 35].

collaboration has often been limited, with inconsistent policies and enforcement measures creating gaps in conflict management. Recent efforts have been made to improve coordination, with both states signing memoranda of understanding to share data on wildlife movements and collaborate on conflict mitigation strategies. To contain the increasing number of human encounters with wildlife, the forest departments of Kerala and Karnataka inked an interstate agreement to collaborate closely to mitigate the challenges posed by wild animals encroaching into human settlements, according to officials aware of the development. The agreement aims to mitigate the challenges posed by wild animals encroaching into human settlements. The agreement focuses on several key aspects, including identifying the root causes of human-wildlife conflicts, delineating conflict zones, streamlining intervention processes to minimise delays, facilitating rapid information exchange, and sharing resources and services.²⁷ As per the agreement, Kerala and Karnataka will jointly map areas prone to wildlife attacks, examine the reasons, avoid delay in tackling the issue and ensure speedy exchange of information between the two sides.

Tracking and Monitoring

Use of Technology: Implementing technology for real-time tracking of wildlife movements, including:

GPS Collaring: Attaching GPS collars to animals to monitor their movements and anticipate crossings into different states.

Camera Traps: Deploying camera traps in potential conflict areas and corridors to observe animal activities and collect data.

Data Sharing: Establishing a centralized database to enable states to access and share information on wildlife movements, incidents, and interventions, which includes:

Movement Patterns: Tracking the migration patterns of animals crossing state boundaries.

Conflict Documentation: Recording conflicts and responses to inform future planning and coordination.

Community Engagement

Involve Local Communities: Engaging local populations living near wildlife habitats in conservation efforts can be beneficial

Education and Awareness: Implementing programs to inform communities about wildlife behavior and peaceful coexistence strategies.

Reporting Mechanisms: Establishing systems for communities to report wildlife sightings and conflicts to state authorities promptly.

²⁷Kerala, Karnataka sign agreement to curb wild animal menace. Collaborative Management Across Jurisdictions) Interstate Agreements and Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs)<https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/humanwildlife-conflicts-karnataka-kerala-ink-pact->

Community-Based Conservation Initiatives: Supporting initiatives that involve local stakeholders in managing wildlife conflicts can include:

Incentives for Conservation: Providing incentives for communities to adopt conservation practices that minimize conflicts.

Local Wildlife Scouts: Training local scouts to monitor and report wildlife movements, creating a bridge between wildlife and state authorities.

Indian Knowledge System Insights into Managing Human-Wildlife Conflicts.

The Indian ancient knowledge system offers holistic, community-oriented, and ecologically grounded approaches to addressing human-wildlife conflicts. By integrating lessons from Ayurveda, sacred groves, Vrikshayurveda, and Dharmic laws, contemporary conservation efforts can enhance human-wildlife relations.²⁸

LEGAL CHALLENGES AND THE WAY FORWARD

Jurisdictional Issues

One of the primary legal challenges in addressing human-wildlife conflict in Kerala and Karnataka is the jurisdictional ambiguity in border areas.²⁵ The current legal framework does not provide clear guidelines for managing wildlife that crosses state boundaries, leading to inconsistent conservation policies.²⁶

Enforcement of Wildlife Protection Laws

Both states face significant challenges in enforcing wildlife protection laws, particularly in remote and forested areas where poaching, illegal logging, and habitat destruction are prevalent.²⁹ Strengthening enforcement mechanisms and ensuring stricter penalties for violators will be essential in mitigating human-wildlife conflicts.

INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVE ON HUMAN-WILDLIFE CONFLICTS

Human-wildlife conflicts are a global issue, impacting both human communities and wildlife conservation efforts across various regions.

Africa: In many African nations, conflicts frequently arise between humans and large mammals such as elephants, lions, and hippos. Elephants are known for raiding crops and damaging property, resulting in significant economic losses for farmers and often leading to

²⁸ <https://iksindia.org/about.php>. The vision of the IKS Division is to rejuvenate and mainstream Indian Knowledge Systems for the contemporary world. The objective of the IKS Division is to completely decolonize Indian mind by generating interest and healthy critical reverence for the unbroken knowledge traditions of Bhārata for the welfare of the world.

²⁹ Government of Kerala, Kerala State Planning Board Fourteenth Five-Year Plan (2022-2027) Working Group on Addressing Issues Related To Human-Wildlife Interactions In Kerala. Report, Agriculture Division March 2022

retaliatory killings. Similarly, lion attacks on livestock create tensions between pastoral communities and conservation authorities.

Asia: Countries like India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka face regular conflicts involving elephants, tigers, and leopards. In India, human-elephant conflicts are particularly common, with elephants damaging crops and property. Tigers and leopards also prey on livestock, leading to retaliatory killings that further strain relationships with local communities.

North America: In North America, conflicts mainly involve bears, wolves, coyotes, and mountain lions. These incidents typically occur where urban development encroaches on wildlife habitats, increasing interactions. Bears are notorious for raiding garbage and causing property damage, which leads to disputes with residents.

South America: In South America, conflicts often involve jaguars, pumas, and monkeys. Jaguars may prey on livestock, creating conflicts with ranchers. Urban expansion and agricultural activities contribute to habitat loss and fragmentation, exacerbating these conflicts.

Australia: In Australia, conflicts generally involve kangaroos, wallabies, and dingoes. Both kangaroos and wallabies can damage crops and compete with livestock for resources, leading to farmer disputes. Dingoes are sometimes seen as pests and are subject to control measures to protect livestock.

International strategies to mitigate human-wildlife conflicts often emphasize habitat conservation, sustainable land use, community engagement, and conflict resolution. Raising awareness about coexistence and promoting sustainable practices are vital for reducing conflicts and supporting global wildlife conservation efforts.

INDIAN PERSPECTIVE ON HUMAN-WILDLIFE CONFLICTS

Human-wildlife conflicts present significant challenges in India, especially where human populations overlap with wildlife habitats. Constitutional mandates, such as Article 48A and Article 51A(g), underscore the state's responsibility to protect the environment and citizens' duty to safeguard wildlife.³⁰ The situation in India is however, changing. Human population increase and its consequent demand for natural resources has led to degradation and fragmentation of natural habitats. As a result, humans and wildlife compete for the same diminishing resources. This shift from co-existence to conflict has the potential to undermine existing and future conservation efforts, and also hinder the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)³¹

Elephant-Human Conflicts: India hosts a large population of wild elephants, primarily found in states like Assam, West Bengal, Karnataka, and Kerala. These elephants often invade agricultural fields in search of food, causing crop damage, property destruction, and even

³⁰<https://legislative.gov.in/constitution-of-india>

³¹<https://www.giz.de/en/html/index.html>

human fatalities. While elephants are culturally revered, the economic losses and safety concerns they generate lead to conflicts.

Tiger and Leopard Conflicts: Significant populations of tigers and leopards also exist in India. Conflicts typically arise when these big cats prey on livestock in villages near forests. Retaliatory killings by villagers pose threats to conservation efforts, and though human attacks are rare, they receive considerable attention and heighten tensions between communities and conservation authorities.

Human-Leopard Conflicts in Urban Areas: Recent years have seen an uptick in human-leopard conflicts in urban and peri-urban regions. Rapid urbanization and habitat encroachment have prompted leopards to enter human settlements in search of prey like dogs and livestock. These encounters can lead to conflicts and, occasionally, attacks on humans, raising safety concerns.

Crop Raiding by Wild Boars and Monkeys: Smaller species, such as wild boars and monkeys, also contribute to human-wildlife conflicts. Wild boars frequently raid agricultural fields, causing economic losses for farmers, while monkey populations often invade crops and garbage bins, leading to nuisances and conflicts.

Conservation Efforts and Mitigation Measures: The Indian government and conservation organizations have implemented various strategies to mitigate human-wildlife conflicts. These include establishing wildlife corridors, constructing fences and trenches to deter crop raiding, compensation schemes for losses, and community-based conservation initiatives. There are ongoing efforts to educate local communities about coexistence with wildlife and promote sustainable livelihood options.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Strengthening the Legal Framework

To address the gaps in the current legal framework, there is a need for stronger legislation that specifically deals with human-wildlife conflict mitigation. This could include amendments to the Wildlife (Protection) Act or the introduction of a separate law governing conflict management. The Wildlife Protection (Amendment) Bill, 2023, provides a promising start in this direction.

Policy and Legal Frameworks: - Strengthen policy and legal frameworks related to wildlife conservation and management, including provisions for compensation, conflict resolution mechanisms, and enforcement of regulations. Ensure that policies and regulations are effectively implemented and enforced at the local level to address human-wildlife conflicts. By implementing these recommendations and suggestions in a coordinated and holistic manner, it is possible to reduce the frequency and severity of human-wildlife conflicts

while promoting the conservation of biodiversity and the well-being of both humans and wildlife.

Cross-State Wildlife Management Task Force

Given the shared ecosystems between Kerala and Karnataka, the formation of a cross-state wildlife management task force would help coordinate conservation efforts, ensure uniform enforcement of laws, and facilitate the sharing of resources and data.

Improving Compensation Schemes

Both states should work to improve the efficiency and accessibility of compensation schemes, ensuring that affected communities receive timely and adequate relief. Simplifying the application process and using technology to expedite verification could reduce bureaucratic delays.

Investment in Habitat Restoration

Restoring degraded habitats is a long-term solution to human-wildlife conflict. By investing in reforestation and creating buffer zones, Kerala and Karnataka can reduce the likelihood of wildlife venturing into human settlements

Education and Awareness: - Conduct educational programs and awareness campaigns to educate communities about the importance of wildlife conservation and promote coexistence with wildlife. People are the key to making conservation work. Provide training and capacity building for local communities, farmers, and forest department personnel on conflict mitigation techniques and wildlife-friendly practices.

Indian knowledge system: Introduce NEP 2020 in all universities and school's syllabus. Merging traditional ecological wisdom with modern science may pave the way for sustainable solutions that foster coexistence rather than conflict between humans and wildlife.

Early Warning Systems and Conflict Monitoring: - Establish early warning systems to alert communities about the presence of wildlife in their vicinity and prevent potential conflicts. Implement systems for monitoring and reporting human-wildlife conflict incidents to track trends, identify hotspots, and inform targeted interventions.

Livelihood Support and Alternative Income Sources: - Provide livelihood support and alternative income sources for communities living in areas prone to human-wildlife conflicts, such as ecotourism, agroforestry, or sustainable agriculture practices. Empower local communities to engage in wildlife-friendly livelihood activities that contribute to conservation efforts. Considering the rising human-wildlife conflict in forest fringe areas, the government has given priority to conflicts mitigation measures in the budget.

A special package will be launched to curb wildlife attacks and protect communities in forest areas and Rs 50 crore has been earmarked for the purpose. Kerala budget boosts funds for human-wildlife conflict mitigation, forest conservation. A special package will be launched to

curb wildlife attacks and protect communities in forest areas and Rs 50 crore has been earmarked for the purpose in 2025-26.

Community-Based Conservation Initiatives: - Implement community-based conservation

initiatives that involve local communities in wildlife management and decision-making processes. Foster partnerships between local communities, government agencies, NGOs, and other stakeholders to collaboratively address human-wildlife conflicts.

CONCLUSION

Human-wildlife conflict is one of the big threats to a lot of wildlife. Human-wildlife conflict in Kerala and Karnataka is a complex issue that requires a multifaceted approach. The Wildlife Protection (Amendment) Bill, 2023, offers new opportunities for addressing legal gaps, but more needs to be done at the state level to ensure effective conflict mitigation. By strengthening the legal framework, enhancing cross-state collaboration, and improving policy interventions, both states can reduce the frequency and severity of conflicts, ensuring a safer coexistence between humans and wildlife. Sustainable solutions for mitigating such conflicts through collaborative efforts between states. Both Kerala and Karnataka have made strides in implementing policies to mitigate conflict, but more needs to be done to harmonize their efforts and improve cross-border collaboration. With stronger legal frameworks, improved compensation systems, and the effective use of technology, these states can reduce the frequency and severity of human-wildlife conflicts, ensuring a safer coexistence between humans and wildlife.